

Mental Health Effects of Floods on Adolescents in Rural Bangladesh: A Qualitative Analysis

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Abstract

The floods in Bangladesh are not an uncommon disaster, and the recent August 2024 floods left deep trauma among people residing in Feni, Noakhali, Cumilla, and Lakshmipur. Among the many losses caused by the floods, their impact on the mental health of adolescents and children is particularly concerning, as these young individuals are especially vulnerable in such traumatic situations. The study explores the psychological impacts of these floods on adolescents aged 14-22 years, examining how displacement, loss of livelihood, and the disruption of education contribute to anxiety, depression, and mental distress in the immediate aftermath of the flood. Seventeen in-depth, semi-structured interviews with victims, along with discussions with family members, have been conducted to understand their emotional responses and uncertainties about the future. The results show a persistent pattern of mental health problems aggravated by poor access to care and the urgent need for targeted interventions. This paper outlines not just the psychosocial struggles of youth from flood-prone areas but also brings forth the need to integrate mental health into disaster relief frameworks in order to build resilience and ensure recovery among such a vulnerable population.

Keywords: extreme weather events; flooding; mental health; stressors; protective factors; adolescents

1. Introduction

Extreme Weather Events (EWEs) are severe, climate-driven phenomena like floods or droughts that disrupt ecosystems, economics, and disproportionately impact vulnerable communities.

UNICEF warns that over two million children are at risk as the worst floods in 34 years devastate eastern Bangladesh, affecting 5.6 million people (1). Nearly half a million people in Bangladesh have sought refuge in schools and temporary

shelters as historic floods affected over 5.8 million people and left at least 52 dead (2). Heavy rainfall has triggered severe flooding across 11 districts in Bangladesh, affecting over 4.9 million people, including more than 2 million children (3).

As climate change accelerates, extreme weather events (EWEs) are occurring more frequently and with greater intensity globally (4). In this context, children and adolescents are particularly vulnerable due to their limited life experience and underdeveloped coping strategies (5). Approximately 25% of children and adolescents exhibit symptoms of

post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, or depression after experiencing Extreme Weather Events (EWEs), according to the American Academy of Pediatrics (6).

Adolescents, being in a critical developmental phase, are particularly vulnerable to stress, anxiety, and trauma induced by natural disasters. Yet, the psychological impact of flooding on this age group in Bangladesh remains largely unexplored. This paper examines the mental health effects of flooding on adolescents in Feni, Noakhali, Cumilla, and Lakshmipur, focusing on anxiety, depression, and coping mechanisms. It aims to assess how flood exposure influences psychological well-being and explore the adaptive strategies adolescents use to manage stress and trauma, highlighting the need for targeted mental health interventions in these vulnerable regions. Besides, understanding the mental health impact of floods on adolescents can inform more effective mental health interventions and disaster response policies in flood-prone regions of Bangladesh.

This paper will begin with a comprehensive review of the existing literature on mental health issues induced by floods. Following this review, an analysis of field data collected from regions affected by flooding will be presented. The paper will conclude with targeted recommendations for enhancing mental health support in disaster-prone areas.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction to Extreme Weather Events (EWEs)

Extreme weather events (EWEs) are characterized by unusual occurrences in a particular location and time of year that deviate significantly from typical climatic patterns, often resulting in severe consequences. Such events encompass a range of phenomena, including heatwaves, droughts, storms, avalanches, and intense precipitation, which frequently lead to flash floods and other related hazards (7). In recent years, climate change has intensified the frequency and severity of extreme weather events (EWEs), such as droughts and floods, on a global scale (8). Notably, flood risk has escalated significantly between 2005 and 2020 (9). Across regions and latitudes worldwide, there has been a marked increase in both the occurrence and duration of prolonged flood events.

2.2 Impact of Floods in Bangladesh

Due to its geographical location, Bangladesh is highly susceptible to recurrent natural disasters, including cyclones, storm surges, floods, and riverbank erosion. Consequently, the country is frequently affected by floods resulting from heavy rainfall and overflowing rivers (10). In fact, Bangladesh experiences cyclones or floods almost annually, with a documented history of 75 severe events of this nature over the past century (11). Natural disasters such as floods have widespread and long-term effects, leading to job losses, reduced income, and property damage (12). These challenges are especially pronounced for low-income populations, who tend to bear a disproportionate share of the burden in the aftermath of such events. In addition, floods in Bangladesh pose significant threats to public health, primarily through

the spread of communicable diseases and malnutrition (13).

2.3 Mental Health and Natural Disasters

Besides the obvious physical health impacts, extreme weather events (EWEs) can have a profound impact on mental health, including increasing the risk of depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), psychological distress, and exacerbating pre-existing mental health conditions (14). While acute stress symptoms may manifest in the immediate aftermath of a flood, common mental health sequelae, over the longer term, include sleep disturbances, concentration problems, and post-traumatic stress symptoms and disorders. Several studies have identified potential long-term mental health consequences that may persist for up to a decade following exposure in communities heavily affected by extreme weather events (EWEs) (15).

2.4 Adolescents: Why They Are Vulnerable and Their Mental Health Impact

While floods and extreme weather events (EWEs) affect all age groups within a community, children and adolescents are especially vulnerable to their harmful effects. Their reliance on caregivers and familiar environments, coupled with their distinct approach to processing traumatic events and limited coping mechanisms, make them especially vulnerable (16). Compared to adults, children, and adolescents exhibit a higher risk of developing psychological distress following disasters due to physiological and cognitive immaturity, limited physical skills, elevated metabolic rate, and dependence on others for care, protection,

safety, and provision (17). The disruption of everyday life, including the cessation of schooling, can be a significant exacerbating factor for their mental health (18). The role of caregivers, such as parents and family, is paramount in supporting children and adolescents during such times (19).

2.5 Gaps in Research and Contribution

Bangladesh, having experienced numerous floods, has seen considerable research on the impacts of these events. However, most of these studies focus primarily on physical health effects, such as infectious diseases, water contamination, and pregnancy-related issues. As a result, research assessing the mental health impacts of floods and other disasters remains limited in Bangladesh. The mental health of adolescents, in particular, tends to be even more overlooked (20). Additionally, existing studies, though based on scenarios from other countries, have often collected data long after the events, with some conducted nearly six years after the 2016 flood (19). As a result, the participants may not accurately recall or share their true emotions from that time. Consequently, there is a lack of data on the immediate mental health impacts following such disasters, and research on the mental health state in the immediate aftermath of devastating floods is scarce. To address this gap, the data have been collected just one to two weeks after the floods, which is a critical period for capturing accurate and relevant information. In some affected districts, water remains stagnant, and many students are still unable to attend schools or colleges. This situation underscores the urgency of assessing mental health impacts during this immediate aftermath. The study focuses

specifically on children and adolescents aged 14-22, aiming to understand the unique psychological effects they experience during and after such disasters. By capturing data at this early stage, the study seeks to provide valuable insights into their immediate mental health challenges, which are often overlooked in broader research.

3. Methods

Using a semi-structured interview guide, the research team conducted interviews with adolescents aged 14-22 from four major flood-affected areas—Cumilla, Noakhali, Feni, and Lakshmipur—during the August flood, as well as with relevant stakeholders, to explore how young people coped with the disaster.

3.1 Research design

The study employed a qualitative phenomenological approach to explore the mental health conditions of adolescents, recognizing that qualitative methods are particularly suited for understanding phenomena from the participants' perspectives. Qualitative research emphasizes how individuals interpret and make sense of their lived experiences (21). Accordingly, the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) has been applied to capture the participants' subjective experiences. IPA aims to explore in detail the processes by which individuals make sense of their personal experiences (22), offering a valuable framework for examining and understanding lived experiences. This approach allows for producing an account of lived experience (23) in the participants' terms, free from pre-existing theoretical frameworks. Furthermore, IPA is particularly well-suited for investigating

complex, ambiguous, and emotionally charged experiences (24).

3.2 Development of the Interview Guide

A semi-structured interview is ideal for the research as it allows flexibility to explore participants' unique experiences while maintaining a consistent framework for gathering in-depth insights into adolescents' mental health during the flooding disaster (18).

The questionnaire is divided into four sections.

1. **General:** These questions explore the respondent's awareness of the flood and its impact on their personal and social environment.
2. **Stressors/Protective Factors:** They focus on emotional responses, coping actions, and perceptions of stress during the flood.
3. **Mental Health Care:** These questions assess the availability of mental health support, personal coping methods, and sources of assistance during the flood.
4. **Reflection:** These questions encourage reflection on support needs, community preparedness, and feedback on the consultation process.

Table 1: the interview guide

Topic	Primary Questions	Follow Up Questions
General	How long have you lived	

	in this area?	
	How did you know about the flood?	What were you doing when you heard of the flood?
	To what extent were you, your family and your social environment affected?	What do you remember about that time?
Stressors/ Protective factors	What were your first feelings and thoughts after knowing about the flood?	How did others perceive the flood?
	If you look back at that time during flood, at which point was your psychological stress the highest? When did you feel most afraid?	How did you feel when the danger was over?
	What was the first thing you did?	
Mental Health Care	Was there any medical or mental health care provide?	How was the medical and psychological care like at that time?
	Have you sought contact with professionals or crisis intervention team?	
	How do you	Do you talk to

	cope when you feel overwhelmed or stressed?	anyone when you feel this way?
		Who do you turn to for support?
		Did you receive any help or support from your neighbors, friends, or community after the flood? What kind of help?
Reflection	Would you like to get more support, e.g., in the form of another consultation?	
	Do you have any suggestions or what should be done in same situations in the future?	
	Do you think there is enough support for people your age in your community?	Do you think your community is prepared for another flood? How does that make you feel?
	How did you feel to talk with us?	
	Is there anything you want to add more?	

3.3 Features of the Study Area

The eastern part of Bangladesh, including the districts of Feni, Comilla, Noakhali, Habiganj, Moulvibazar, Khagrachhari, and Rangamati, experienced severe flooding starting on August 20, 2024, as a result of intense rainfall and rising water levels (25).

Among the affected areas, Feni, Cumilla, Noakhali, and Lakshmipur were identified as some of the most severely impacted districts. Consequently, the team focused on visiting the most rural parts of these regions to gather authentic accounts from adolescents who experienced the devastating flood firsthand.

3.4 Sampling and sample size

The ideal sample size for qualitative studies varies depending on the study design and respondent characteristics. Sandelowski suggested that a sample size of 10 may suffice for studies involving homogeneous groups (26). Crouch and McKenzie further argued that fewer than 20 participants can foster better communication by allowing researchers to build closer relationships with respondents (27). According to Charmaz (28), 25 participants is a suitable number for smaller projects, while Green and Thorogood (29) noted that leading qualitative researchers often use samples of 20 or more participants. In contrast, Modell (30), as revised by Guest et al. (31), emphasized the importance of 15 respondents for systematic qualitative case studies. Hieronimi et al. (32) conducted 9 interviews for the Qualitative Study to Explain the Factors Influencing Mental Health after a Flooding.

For the study, a total of 17

Individuals were interviewed, employing purposive sampling to ensure the selection of participants who could provide the most relevant and insightful perspectives. The participants ranged in age from 12 to 23 years, with an average age of 17.8 ± 3.5 years. This method allowed us to focus on respondents whose experiences aligned closely with the research objectives, enhancing the depth and quality of the findings. Of the participants, 9 were males (53%) and 8 were females (47%), ensuring a balanced representation of perspectives in the study.

3.5 Data Collection

For this study, inclusion and exclusion criteria was established prior to data collection. Only respondents meeting these criteria were selected for participation. The criteria are detailed below:

1. Adolescents aged 14 to 22 years, or family members of these adolescents.
2. Individuals who experienced the loss of personal property or belongings due to the flood.

One member of the research team (Md. Ashraful Islam) and two well-trained volunteers conducted semi-structured interviews utilizing the interview guide described previously. Following three preliminary interviews, the research guideline questions were revised to optimize the efficacy of subsequent interviews. The interviews were scheduled in October and were conducted in person within a confidential setting, such as the respondents' homes. Participants had the option to choose the location for their interview. Each interview took place in a private setting, ensuring that they could

freely and comfortably share their deep and personal experiences.

The interviews were audio-recorded, and post-interview summaries were prepared to reflect on the session, briefly describe the interview context, and note specific details. The interviews were conducted in Bangla, with relevant citations subsequently translated into English. The duration of each interview ranged from 10 to 30 minutes, with an average length of approximately 15 minutes. To prevent potential re-traumatization, the transcripts were not sent back to the interviewees for review or correction.

3.6 Ethical Consideration

All interviewees participated voluntarily, provided informed verbal consent and were free to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any disadvantages.

3.7 Data Analysis

The transcripts were analyzed using qualitative content analysis according to Rädiker and Kuckartz (33), a method suitable for interpreting qualitative data by systematically categorizing text passages. This approach facilitates the identification and analysis of meaningful aspects within the data (34). Initially, a priori categories were established based on literature, the interview guide, and the research questions. During the inductive phase of category development, the initial codes were expanded or refined through iterative review of the transcripts (35). This process involved assigning text passages to various categories based on the evolving code system. The final code system was developed through a mixed deductive-inductive approach, employing

subsumption strategies to create both overarching categories and subcategories.

To ensure the robustness of the coding process, different experts compared their interpretations of codes and categories with those applied by the interviewer. This peer review facilitated a discussion on differing perspectives and interpretations. The coding process allowed for the formation of thematic clusters, identification of repetitions and patterns, and recognition of outliers.

Data analysis was conducted using NVIVO.12, and the results of a short questionnaire were analyzed in Excel and integrated with the transcribed interviews in NVIVO.12. The findings from the interviews provided contextual and background information but were not subjected to theoretical triangulation.

4. Results

4.1 Direct Mental Health Consequences: Impact of Flood-Induced Trauma and Displacement

4.1.1 Psychological Shock Due to Unpreparedness

The most prevalent and common theme that emerged from the interviews conducted with adolescents and children is the profound psychological shock experienced due to their first encounter with a flood. For many of the participants, this event marked an unprecedented experience, as even their previous generations had not faced a flood of this magnitude. The suddenness of the event contributed significantly to their distress, as they were unaccustomed to such

circumstances and had no prior frame of reference to guide them in coping with the situation

“I’ve spoken with my father, grandfather, and even older generations. None of them have ever experienced a flood in this area.

Even a 90-year-old man said he hadn’t seen anything like this in his lifetime.”

(Feni, male, 19)

Compounding this sense of shock was the lack of any prior warning regarding the impending flood. The rapid rise in water levels took the adolescents by surprise, leaving them with little to no time for preparation or evacuation. This unforeseen occurrence not only heightened their anxiety but also left them feeling powerless and confused in the face of a natural disaster that they had only heard about in stories.

One participant described the experience as follows:

“After seeing the water level rise overnight, I did not know if I was going to survive. I witnessed everything being destroyed by the flood right in front of me, which was utterly shocking.”

(Cumilla, Female, 18)

“At first, we thought the water level was rising normally and would decrease by evening, just like before. But when it continued to rise through the night, we were shocked. We never imagined there would be a flood in Feni, so we couldn’t make a single preparation.”

(Feni, male, 19)

“The only thing running through my mind was will I survive? I just wanted to live.”

(Female, 17)

This lack of preparedness and the overwhelming destruction that followed left the victims in a state of shock, further exacerbating the psychological impact on these communities.

4.1.2 Aversion to Study or education-related Psychological Impact

Young adolescents and school-aged children severely affected by the recent floods show a marked aversion to studying. Many have lost essential materials, including textbooks and documents, due to water damage. The destruction of their homes has worsened their economic conditions, leading to widespread food insecurity. As a result, the prospect of returning to school feels increasingly unattainable, leaving many students mentally and emotionally devastated.

“I don't have the desire to study anymore.”

(Feni, female, 19)

Some children express a desire to continue their education but cite their family’s financial struggles as a barrier. This situation has created tremendous mental challenges, with students overwhelmed by worries about their future.

“My family has lost everything. We don’t even know what we’ll eat or where we’ll live. I don’t think I’ll ever be able to go to school again.”

(Feni, female, 19)

4.1.3 Shelter Crisis

The majority of affected individuals have lost their homes and are now primarily residing on the streets or in nearby schools. This precarious living situation

has left adolescents and children mentally unstable, as they face continuous fear and anxiety due to the absence of a safe place to live. The constant threat of further environmental instability exacerbates their emotional distress, making it increasingly challenging for them to cope with their circumstances.

“When you see there’s no home left for you... that feeling, I felt the same.”
(Cumilla, male, 19)

“All we have left is the bare ground; the current has taken everything else.”
(Cumilla, male, 19)

Many respondents reported severe disruptions to their household stability. One individual shared their ongoing struggle with homelessness:

“My family lost our shelter, and we have been living on the streets for 27 days. We need a place to live, but the government has yet to take any action.”
(Cumilla, Male, 21)

The uncertainty surrounding housing and the lack of immediate relief has left many feeling isolated and abandoned. The ongoing fear of further loss is also contributing to their emotional distress. As one participant expressed:

“I am constantly afraid due to our unstable shelter. We have a damaged house that could collapse at any moment. Every night, I sleep with the fear of losing everything again.”
(Feni, Female, 19)

The psychological impact of losing shelter and living in precarious conditions has led to significant emotional distress, with many individuals expressing feelings of helplessness and fear for the future.

4.1.4 Females’ Insecurity and Safety Concerns

This theme was notably prevalent among female interviewees.

As water levels rose, individuals of all genders were compelled to seek refuge in local centers, where overcrowding emerged as a significant concern. In these makeshift shelters, many young women encountered discomfort and a pervasive sense of insecurity, as the presence of numerous unfamiliar individuals fostered an unsafe environment. Although they did not face direct physical harm, the absence of proactive safety measures from local authorities or government representatives exacerbated the vulnerability felt by female refugees.

The flood, coupled with various accompanying challenges, was sufficient to leave young female adolescents mentally distressed. This sense of insecurity represented an additional layer of psychological pressure, compounding their existing anxieties.

One participant shared her experience:

“None of the local leaders or government members assured safety for women. Although we didn’t face any trouble, I felt uncomfortable and unsafe during my time at the refugee center.”
(Feni, Female, 18)

4.1.5 Health Struggles and Mental Breakdown

The floods have severely compromised access to clean drinking water, resulting in outbreaks of waterborne diseases such as diarrhea and skin infections.

This health crisis has induced significant anxiety among residents, many of whom are fearful of contracting serious illnesses. A 17-year-old boy from Feni remarked,

"I have had diarrhea for the last six days, and I cannot sleep properly, constantly worrying about the potential for other diseases."

A parent recounted the struggles faced by their child, stating,

"My son has developed a skin infection over the past few days, and it is worsening."

Severe shortages of food and clothing compound health issues, further undermining both physical and mental well-being. Many individuals report inadequate nutrition, leading to starvation, while the lack of clothing increases the risk of skin infections. This combination of physical deprivation and health struggles is contributing to a profound sense of hopelessness and mental distress among the affected populations.

4.2 Stressors: Factors Contributing to Psychological Distress Among Flood-Affected Youth

4.2.1 Family Concern & Community Concern

Adolescents and children have shown significant concern for their families, often experiencing distress over their well-being and safety.

"I was in town when my family called me in the evening. Suddenly, they started to scream and cry!"

"When I got home, I couldn't find any of my family. I had no idea where they were or if they had even survived. I sat on the road the whole night, waiting for them."

They are concerned not only for their family members but also for neighbors and others living together in emergency shelters, such as schools.

"We can't take the pregnant and sick woman to the hospital. There's no way... all the roads are underwater."

4.2.2 Distress Over Domestic Animal Suffering

A significant portion of the rural population in Bangladesh relies heavily on domestic animals, such as cows and goats, for their livelihoods. These animals are not only used for farming, milk production, and meeting nutritional needs, but they also form a crucial part of the financial stability of these communities. During the floods, some families were able to save their animals, while others were not as fortunate. However, even for those who managed to rescue their livestock, the lack of available food became a critical issue, as grazing lands were submerged, leading to widespread animal deaths due to starvation. This situation not only resulted in financial instability but also profound emotional distress, as many villagers had developed deep-rooted emotional bonds with their animals. The adolescents and children have shown a big concern for the survival of their pet animals. This is posing a deep on their mental health.

A local stakeholder shared a similar experience:

"I lost two cows and one goat. I don't know how I will regain financial stability after this. My daughter, who spent the most time with the animals, was extremely saddened by losing them."

Those who managed to save their animals are now struggling to feed them, as the lack of available food has become critical due to submerged grazing lands.

"We couldn't save anything except our cow. Now, it's living with us on the road.

We're getting relief for the people, but what about the cow? What will it eat? How will it survive?"

This situation has had a profound and adverse impact on the younger demographic. Adolescents and children, in particular, have exhibited significant distress over the plight of their pets. Many of those interviewed expressed deep sorrow and concern for their animals' well-being.

4.2.3 Identity Crisis

The recent floodwaters have washed away crucial personal documents, such as school certificates, identification cards, and other credentials. For many students, this loss has induced a profound sense of uncertainty and distress, as these documents are integral to their identity as students. In the absence of these credentials, some individuals are experiencing a deep-seated identity crisis, feeling disconnected from the achievements and progress they have worked so hard to attain.

Without these essential documents, many fear they will be unable to continue their education or prove their qualifications in the future, fostering a growing sense of

helplessness. This emotional distress is further exacerbated by the uncertainty surrounding their living conditions and disrupted educational pathways, intensifying the overwhelming sense of loss—not only of their physical belongings but also of their clear sense of self and future direction.

One participant expressed this anxiety, stating:

"I lost my school certificate, ID card, and all other important documents. I don't know how I will recover my credentials. I feel like I've lost my identity."

(Feni, Male, 15)

"No proof that I am a student? What is my Identity?"

(Feni, Male, 19)

4.2.4 Trauma from Death and Fear

One of the most harrowing experiences reported during the flood was witnessing the loss of life firsthand. For many individuals, the sight of dead bodies being swept away by the floodwaters was both shocking and deeply traumatic. These events were completely unexpected, as few had ever been confronted with such a stark reminder of mortality. The inability to provide proper burials or say farewell to loved ones only intensified the emotional burden, leaving many individuals in a state of shock and psychological distress.

One participant recounted:

"I was shocked to see dead bodies, and we couldn't do anything, not even give them a proper farewell. I'm still in shock."

(Cumilla, Male, 22)

"We cried a lot!"

“We found three dead bodies in the water. Later, we buried them on the little existing ground.”

(Feni, 18, Female)

Reports of snake bites resulting from rising floodwaters have intensified mental trauma among some children. The fear of encountering snakes in their temporary shelters adds to their anxiety, exacerbating their already precarious situation.

“Snakes were everywhere, and I was too afraid to even get down from the bed. I kept thinking that one might bite me.”

4.2.5 Isolation and Relief Inaccessibility

The devastating impact of the recent floods has resulted in the collapse of transportation systems, rendering affected communities inaccessible to medical assistance. Consequently, the lack of timely relief has fostered a profound sense of isolation among residents. One participant articulated this feeling, stating,

"We are disconnected from the outside world. Nobody can hear us; we cannot go outside from this place because of the lack of transportation"

(Lakshmipur, Male, 22)

Moreover, many individuals report significant psychological distress stemming from food shortages, loss of electricity, communication disruptions, and inadequate relief efforts. Their inability to connect with friends and relatives contributes to a sense of isolation and heightened anxiety. A participant from Noakhali expressed,

"For the first few days, we received some relief, but now, nothing. Moreover, there

is no way to communicate with others. I'm getting weaker mentally every day"
(Noakhali, female, 21).

“There’s been no electricity for 13 days. No internet either. We can’t call anyone... We have no idea how our friends and relatives are doing, or even if they’re alive. It feels like we’re stranded on an island.”

(Sonagazi, male, 17)

While relief efforts are underway, many affected individuals are unable to access assistance due to the surrounding floodwaters. This inability to obtain aid serves as an additional source of mental stress for those already struggling with their circumstances.

"The saddest part is, the relief is coming, but it can't reach us. The roads are all underwater... relief trucks can't even make it to our village."

4.3 Protective Factors: Elements Supporting Resilience and Coping in Flood-Affected Communities

4.3.1 Family

Amid the devastation caused by the flood, the mental health and emotional well-being of many individuals were largely sustained by family members, as there were few formal support systems in place. For most, families, especially mothers, played a critical role in providing the emotional support needed to cope with the crisis.

“Who can I share my thoughts with, except for my mother?”

“I received mental support only from my mother.”

(Noakhali, Female, 16)

“My uncle kept telling me that everything would be fine, Inshallah.”

4.3.2 Community Support

Despite the lack of organized psychological support, the flood also brought out resilience and leadership in some individuals. Certain members of the community stepped up, volunteering and forming small groups to assist others, which not only helped the affected population but also fostered a sense of purpose and solidarity during the crisis.

As one volunteer stated:

“I couldn’t sit inside the refugee center. I decided to volunteer, thinking I could help others during this hard time.”
(Lakshmipur, Male, 20)

This proactive response, driven by a desire to contribute and support the community, highlights how adversity can inspire leadership and collective action. While the flood caused widespread distress, it also demonstrated the potential for resilience, with some individuals emerging as community leaders, offering both physical aid and a sense of hope to those around them.

4.4 Miscellaneous: Additional Challenges and Concerns in the Aftermath of the Flood

4.4.1 Disparities in Flood Impact

This phenomenon presents a striking contrast. While the flood had a profoundly negative impact on the mental health of

the majority of adolescents, a small yet notable segment of the youth exhibited resilience due to their privileged circumstances.

The primary factor behind their relative stability was that their financial providers, typically their fathers, were employed abroad as foreign laborers. Consequently, while many families experienced a cessation of income, this group remained largely unaffected in terms of lifestyle. Their financial security, coupled with access to alternative housing in urban areas, allowed many of them to relocate to cities, thereby mitigating the adverse effects of the disaster and securing a more favorable living environment.

Upon further questioning, this individual explained:

“My family had a house in town as well, so we shifted there the day after the flood started.”

For one individual, experiencing a flood for the first time initially brought a sense of excitement, although this initial reaction quickly shifted as the reality of the disaster set in.

“When I woke up in the morning and saw water everywhere, I was excited to see it for the first time. I even started fishing”
(Lakshmipur, Male, 19)

4.4.2 Future Recovery Concerns

In the aftermath of the flood, a pervasive sense of uncertainty and fear about the future looms over the affected communities. Both male and female survivors express deep concerns about their ability to recover and rebuild their lives. The devastation has left many

without the financial stability, educational opportunities, and essential resources they once had, creating a bleak outlook for their future prospects.

“We lost over 300,000 BDT due to the loss of fish from our hatchery.”
(Noakhali, Female, 17)

The uncertainty about how, or if, they will be able to return to a stable life has become a major source of anxiety.

One individual shared their fears:

“I’m very confused and have extreme fear about the future. Can I make it? I’m not sure.”
(Noakhali, Female, 23)

This widespread fear of the future is rooted in the loss of livelihoods, disrupted education, and destroyed property, leaving many unsure of how to move forward. With limited access to resources, employment, and support systems, the path to recovery appears daunting. These concerns about the future not only affect their current mental state but also place an emotional burden on individuals who are already grappling with the trauma of the disaster.

“Maybe I can catch up on my studies; I can buy books and learn again. But what about our house? We’ve lost it. How will we recover, and how will we start over?”

The uncertainty surrounding future recovery is a crucial aspect of the long-term psychological impact of the flood on the affected population.

“Five to ten years won't be enough to recover and start over.”

4.4.3 Mental Health Support: Essential Resources and

Interventions for Flood-Affected Individuals

Many individuals reported receiving food relief, but there was a glaring absence of medical aid in the most affected areas. This lack of access to essential healthcare and medicine exacerbated the physical and mental toll on flood victims, who were left to fend for themselves in dire conditions.

One individual highlighted this gap:

“Although we received some food as relief, we didn’t get any medical support or medicine.”
(Feni, Male, 17)

Without timely medical intervention, vulnerable populations faced heightened risks of illness, injury, and mental distress, further compounding the challenges posed by the disaster.

However, in some areas, medical support teams were present to provide assistance with medications and other healthcare needs.

“There was enough medical support; the army was helping us, and relief efforts were underway. Different organizations and volunteers were present as well.”

However, throughout all the interviews, there was no mention of any mental health support teams to help individuals overcome their existing trauma.

5. Discussion

Direct mental health consequences	Stressors	Protective factors
Sudden shock due to lack of preparedness.	Worries for close family members and relatives	Family as a source of shelter and support
Safety concerns and insecurity of females in emergency shelters.	Identity crisis stemming from property loss	Expressing emotions with family members, especially mother
Mental stress due to lack of shelter or housing	Trauma from witnessing dead bodies and snake bites	Assisting others through volunteer efforts
Damage to study materials causing emotional strain	Concerns for domestic animals	Finding comfort in community bonds during hardship
Struggling with diseases and health challenges	Isolation and inaccessibility to relief	
	Disruptions in daily life	

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

To facilitate a clearer understanding of mental health, the discussion has been organized into several sections.

5.1.1 Family: A Dual Role as Both Stressor and Protective Factor

The role of the family emerged as a pivotal factor, functioning both as a source of distress and as a protective influence for adolescents during the flood. From the interviews, it became evident that young people were deeply concerned about the safety and well-being of their families. Several participants mentioned that they were living in towns due to their educational commitments when they received alarming news about their families being in danger due to the flood. In response, many rushed back to their villages. Upon arrival, they faced the distressing reality that they could not immediately reunite with their families, as most were evacuated to emergency shelters such as nearby schools and madrassas. This separation, in addition to the lack of electricity and communication channels, left many adolescents in a state of heightened anxiety about their families' well-being for several days. This phenomenon is similar to the existing study (18).

On the other hand, the family acted as an important and effective protective factor, particularly for younger children who lacked the experience to cope with such crises. Families, especially mothers, played a vital role in alleviating the mental distress of the young individuals. Many adolescents reported that they shared their emotional struggles with their mothers, who provided crucial emotional support during this period. This highlights how living with family offered these adolescents not only physical safety but

also the emotional resilience needed to fight with the trauma of the flood. The emotional support from family members, particularly mothers, was critical in helping young people manage their distress and face the challenges posed by the disaster.

This also indicates that adolescents were significantly reliant on their caregivers, a finding that aligns with prior research (36) (37).

5.1.2 First Impressions and Perceptions of Floods in Young People

The first impression of the flood among adolescents was extremely shocking, as evident in all the interviews. Interviews revealed that many individuals, including their elders and ancestors, did not anticipate a flood in their area and, as a result, failed to prepare adequately for the impending disaster. By the time they realized the severity of the situation, it was too late to take effective action. This unexpected event led to significant losses, and its psychological impact was especially pronounced among young people, who often lack the maturity and coping skills to handle such traumatic experiences. The sudden and unforeseen nature of the disaster intensified feelings of helplessness and anxiety within this vulnerable group.

5.1.3 Coping Mechanisms

The interviews revealed several coping mechanisms among the adolescents. Initially, young people relied heavily on the support of their families to manage the situation. Over time, they also began to engage with their community and neighbors. Many took part in volunteer

work, aiding those who were suffering due to the disaster. They felt a strong responsibility to stand by others and offer help to those in need. Their involvement in relief efforts, such as distributing aid, gave them a sense of purpose and control. This collective participation not only strengthened community bonds but also helped ease the psychological trauma these adolescents were experiencing. By actively contributing to the well-being of others, they discovered a positive outlet for their own distress, which greatly aided their ability to cope with difficult circumstances.

5.1.4 Socioeconomic Conditions Impacting Mental Health

An unexpected finding emerged from the research regarding the mental health conditions of the participants. The authors did not anticipate encountering any positive mental health indicators among the interviewees; however, a slightly favorable mental health condition has been discovered among individuals from privileged backgrounds. This phenomenon was primarily attributed to the fact that the primary earners in their families resided abroad, which provided them with financial stability and the ability to relocate temporarily. As a result, they were less adversely affected by the floods compared to others.

This finding underscores a significant disparity between the financially privileged class and the majority of the population in terms of the impact of the floods. For the privileged class, the flood represented an unusual event that sparked curiosity rather than fear. Some individuals even took the opportunity to engage in fishing, viewing the situation as a novel experience. This stark contrast

highlights the varying degrees of vulnerability and resilience within different socioeconomic levels in the face of natural disasters.

5.1.5 Challenges in Education

One major issue that emerged following the flood was the concern surrounding education, which considerably increased mental health pressure on adolescents. Many of these young individuals, along with their families, lost their homes, and they are now living on roads and emergency shelters without having any permanent place for residence. Additionally, they lost essential belongings and everyday necessities, disrupting their sense of usual life. For students, the loss of study materials, including textbooks, was particularly distressing. More critically, several interviewees highlighted the loss of important documents such as certificates and identification cards, which are essential for proving their student status and personal identity. This led to deep feelings of uncertainty, as many began to question their sense of self—wondering who they were, where they belonged, and if they could still identify as students without these vital documents. This identity crisis significantly impacted their mental health, intensifying feelings of disorientation and anxiety.

In addition, many young people no longer want to continue their studies. Firstly, the loss of critical documentation has made it difficult for them to resume their education. Secondly, the financial hardships faced by their families make it impossible to support their educational pursuits. Having lost nearly everything, these families are struggling for basic survival—they are even uncertain about how to earn a living, what to eat, or where to live. As a result, even those adolescents

who wish to continue their education are unable to do so due to their families' financial incapacity. This underscores a significant challenge faced by flood-affected youth in maintaining their academic aspirations.

5.1.6 Trauma-Worsening Existing Mental Health Conditions

While young people were already suffering from the existing situation, several specific factors further exacerbated their mental distress.

Firstly, some of the interviewees reported witnessing dead bodies being carried away by the floodwaters. This traumatic experience was identified as a remarkable source of psychological distress, as children and adolescents faced the unprecedented horror of encountering mortality at such a young age. Already overwhelmed by the devastation and the struggle for survival, the sight of deceased individuals had a profound and lasting impact on their mental health. Additionally, the inability to perform traditional burial rituals due to the lack of dry ground deepened their grief and helplessness. Again, some bodies could not even be recovered, as they were swept away by the floodwaters.

Secondly, the threat of snake bites further contributed to their psychological distress. Floodwaters often carried venomous snakes into the affected areas, resulting in numerous reports of snake attacks. This created widespread fear among the children, some of whom became so traumatized that they refused to leave elevated spaces or even go outside. The constant fear of snake bites, combined with the traumatic exposure to death and

destruction, imposed a significant mental health burden on the young people interviewed. Both witnessing dead bodies and fearing snake bites emerged as recurrent themes in the interviews, emphasizing their intense impact on the mental state of the children and adolescents. These events contributed to the severe stress and trauma that now define the mental health landscape of flood-affected youth in these regions.

Thirdly, isolation and communication barriers caused by prolonged electricity failures and flooded roads created a sense of disconnection among young people, making them feel cut off from the rest of the country. With no means to access information or stay updated on external events, this isolation has become a significant contributor to their mental health crisis.

Fourthly, the inability to attend school, socialize with friends, or engage in recreational activities has exacerbated feelings of loneliness and emotional distress. Many guardians and stakeholders have observed these youths as consistently gloomy and depressed; this situation, undoubtedly, reflects their heightened sense of isolation and lack of social interaction. The prolonged separation from peers and normal activities is a critical factor in their deteriorating mental health.

5.1.7 Gender Vulnerability

The interviews with female participants revealed another critical issue often overlooked in emergency situations: their sense of insecurity when living in crowded, mixed-gender spaces. Several participants expressed discomfort and hesitation about staying in temporary shelters, such as nearby schools, where they had to share

open spaces with large groups of men. Additionally, many reported inadequate access to proper sanitary facilities, further contributing to their distress. This combination of physical insecurity and poor sanitary conditions, therefore, created notable mental anxiety, which was a recurring theme among the female participants.

5.1.8 Concerns for Domestic Animals

A very interesting and unprecedented finding emerged from the interviews: the concern for domestic animals. This factor represents a significant stressor affecting the mental health of adolescents during the floods, largely due to their strong emotional attachment to pets and livestock. In rural Bangladesh, domestic animals serve as vital sources of livelihood and integral family members, fostering deep emotional bonds. During the floods, unfortunately, few individuals were able to rescue their livestock and pets. Consequently, it resulted in heartbreaking losses that profoundly impacted families, particularly younger members, as it felt akin to losing someone very close.

For those who managed to save their domestic animals, anxiety persisted. Because, while authorities provided food and relief for humans, no resources were allocated for the animals. With all the land submerged, there were no shelters for livestock. Interviews revealed that many young people were deeply concerned about the survival and well-being of their pets and livestock, highlighting a unique aspect of mental health impacts during floods. This illustrates that the loss or endangerment of domestic animals considerably influences the emotional and psychological well-being of flood-affected adolescents and children.

5.1.9 Navigating Recovery Amidst Losses

The region has experienced a massive economic disaster: most earning individuals are currently unable to work. Many have lost their homes and properties, resulting in profound psychological trauma. When young individuals witness the destruction of their homes by floodwaters, it leaves a lasting impact on their mental well-being. Every interviewee expressed deep sorrow over the loss of their houses and personal belongings. This situation underscores the critical link between displacement and psychological trauma among flood-affected youth.

The families of these young individuals have suffered a complete collapse of their financial systems. Those who relied on manual labor can no longer work, while farmers have lost their crops and lands for harvesting. Similarly, those in the fishing industry have seen their stocks and hatcheries destroyed, wiping out their livelihoods. This widespread economic devastation has triggered a severe financial crisis in the affected communities, with young people feeling the impact acutely. They are deeply worried about their future and their ability to recover from the current situation. The loss of their family's income has made them face an uncertain and difficult future, and it has added to their stress and worry about how they will rebuild their lives. These miserable conditions of young people is confirmed by the existing study (38).

5.1.10 Mental Health Support Landscape

The young people affected by the floods faced vulnerable conditions, both physically and mentally. However, there was a clear imbalance in the distribution of medical support teams across the flood-affected areas. In the interviews, 10 participants (59%) reported that there was medical health support available, while 7 participants (41%) indicated that no such support existed.

One troubling and consistent finding, however, was the complete absence of mental health support teams specifically addressing the needs of young adolescents. Despite the urgency of the situation, there was no dedicated effort by authorities or organizations to provide psychological counseling or mental health services, which are, in fact, critical for helping young people recover from such traumatic events. Adolescents need professional mental health care to process their experiences and begin healing. Instead, they were left to cope on their own, relying solely on their families and communities for emotional support. This lack of mental health intervention highlights a notable gap in disaster response and recovery efforts.

5.2 Implications for Mental Health Interventions

Measures must be tailored specifically to address each identified problem and sector discussed.

Given that young people rely heavily on their families and caregivers for support during difficult times, it is crucial that families receive training on how to effectively engage with them in the aftermath of extreme weather events.

Both Hieronimi et al. (39) and Schürr et al. (40), emphasize the importance of

training first responders to engage effectively with parents. This support is essential for helping parents interact with their adolescents after an extreme weather event (EWE). Additionally, these studies reference existing recommendations for parents (41). The findings of this study further confirm that implementing such measures is necessary for fostering healthier family dynamics and better supporting young individuals during recovery.

Also, the trauma and memory or effect can last long (18). This underscores the need for adapted crisis intervention methods, a sentiment echoed in the literature (41). Several approaches can be implemented to minimize stressors and strengthen protective factors.

One potential strategy is to introduce adapted crisis interventions, such as offering classes in schools after an EWE. These classes provide adolescents with a safe space to share their experiences and concerns, potentially with the involvement of a professional. Daniel and Michaela associated supportive counseling with reduced mental distress and its ability to mitigate vulnerability factors (42), which further supports this approach. This aligns with the identified need for non-compulsory care services following a flood. Additionally, such interventions could help alleviate the stress caused by a lack of daily structure and aid in restoring familiar routines as quickly as possible.

Besides the families, the education sector requires more serious attention. Authorities should take the necessary steps to provide students with the documents they have lost, as well as the books and educational materials they need. This support would enable them to quickly return to their normal lives, attend school, and continue their education,

thereby alleviating their distress. Furthermore, it would facilitate their reintegration with peers, promoting social interaction and emotional well-being.

Female insecurity is another significant and pressing concern that warrants urgent attention. Although this issue is unavoidable, measures should be implemented to at least separate the rooms for men and women in emergency shelters. Otherwise, the existing distress will likely escalate, as noted by several female interviewees.

The survival and suffering of domestic animals, surprisingly, emerged as a significant concern in the study, highlighting the worries of their owners. Therefore, relief efforts should also include provisions for animal feed and other measures to support domestic animals, particularly those most commonly kept, such as cows and goats.

From all the discussion and throughout the study, the gap in the mental health sector, specially for young people, becomes obvious. In a developing country like Bangladesh, mental health is frequently overlooked. However, the study demonstrates that flood-affected young people experience significant mental strain and distress, in addition to physical health problems. But there is, unfortunately, a lack of professional support to address these issues. While establishing a robust mental health support system cannot happen overnight, it is essential to begin the process, even with very small initiatives. For example: each medical team should include one or two members dedicated to provide counseling for young people, creating a safe space for them to express their thoughts without judgment. Ultimately, this need for mental health support is the

most pressing issue identified throughout the whole study.

5.3 Strengths & Limitations

This study has several strengths. The most remarkable strength is that it serves as one of the first, if not the baseline, studies addressing the mental health of adolescents and young people affected by a disaster—specifically floods—in Bangladesh. Given the lack of substantial research on this topic, this study can act as a foundational reference for future research in this field.

Another key strength is the timing of the interviews. These were conducted just 2-3 weeks after the disaster, when some areas were still waterlogged, allowing us to capture the participants' fresh emotions and experiences. This timing provided valuable insight into how the affected individuals perceived the disaster and its immediate impact on their mental health.

Moreover, the study identifies direct mental health consequences, stressors, and protective factors, offering critical insights into the mental health support needed in the aftermath of extreme weather events (EWEs). More importantly, the findings highlight the absence of mental health support teams, and thus, no doubt, point out an area where both authorities and organizations must improve their disaster response strategies.

Further research opportunities also arise from this study. None of the interviewees reported feeling burdened or retraumatized by participating; in fact, many expressed satisfaction with the opportunity to share their experiences. The research was conducted following the COREQ (43) criteria, ensuring that robust

scientific methods for qualitative research were adhered to.

However, the study does have limitations. The interviews were conducted only with participants who willingly chose to engage. Those who opted not to participate may have been more traumatized, and their perspectives are missing from the findings. This limitation suggests that the study may not fully capture the broader range of mental health impacts, particularly from those who were most severely affected.

Most of the interviewees were male, although there was a notable number of female participants. However, the predominance of male respondents may indicate that the study somewhat underrepresents the perspective of girls. Given that the research was conducted in rural and underdeveloped areas, where women and girls are often less empowered and less likely to participate in interviews, this may have limited the inclusion of female voices. Hence, the study may lack a comprehensive understanding of the mental health impact on females, emphasizing the need for future research that focuses specifically on adolescent girls and young women in similar contexts.

Additionally, the study was limited to four specific areas that were hit by sudden flooding. While the data collected is accurate for these regions, the findings may not necessarily be representative of other areas of Bangladesh that experience different types of flooding or other disasters. Further studies in diverse geographic locations would help provide a more comprehensive picture of the mental health impacts across the country.

Another limitation is that the study focused solely on the immediate aftermath and short-term mental health

consequences of the flood. There is a clear need for in-depth research exploring the long-term mental health effects of extreme weather events (EWEs) on adolescents. Longitudinal studies could provide valuable insights into how mental health challenges evolve over time and what long-term interventions are necessary for recovery.

Finally, it is important to note that different researchers might have interpreted and coded the data differently, which could introduce variability in findings. To increase validity, several strategies have been employed, such as iterative coding processes and structured discussions among the research team to resolve disagreements and reduce bias during data analysis. This approach strengthens the study's methodological rigor, but it also underscores the importance of transparency and reflexivity in qualitative research.

6. Conclusion

The study highlights that adolescents are highly vulnerable to mental health challenges after extreme weather events (EWEs). Improving access to mental health care and increasing awareness among students, families, and stakeholders are crucial for minimizing the psychological impact. Mental health remains an underrated aspect of disaster recovery, and further research is needed in this field. Prioritizing mental well-being, enhancing care accessibility, and fostering community awareness are essential steps in supporting adolescent mental health after EWEs. This approach will help build resilience and ensure a more effective recovery process.

AI Support

AI assistance has been used in order to enhance the clarity and language of the paper, ensuring better articulation without direct copying & pasting. The AI-supported rephrasing has been used to convey the ideas more effectively while maintaining originality.

References

1. UNICEF. Two million children at risk as worst floods in three decades lash through eastern Bangladesh - UNICEF. 2024 [cited 2024 Sep 24]. Two million children at risk as worst floods in three decades lash through eastern Bangladesh - UNICEF. Available from: <https://www.unicef.org/press-releases/two-million-children-risk-worst-floods-three-decades-lash-through-eastern-bangladesh>
2. ReliefWeb. Bangladesh floods leave more than half a million stranded. 2024 [cited 2024 Sep 24]. Bangladesh floods leave more than half a million stranded - Bangladesh | ReliefWeb. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/report/bangladesh/bangladesh-floods-leave-more-half-million-stranded>
3. Save the Children. Save the Children | Bangladesh. 2024 [cited 2024 Sep 24]. Save the Children is with 2 million flood-affected children and adolescents | Bangladesh. Available from: <https://bangladesh.savethechildren.net/news/save-children-2-million-flood-affected-children-and-adolescents>
4. Watts N, Amann M, Arnell N, Ayeb-Karlsson S, Beagley J, Belesova K, et al. The 2020 report of The Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: responding to converging crises. *The Lancet*. 2021 Jan;397(10269):129–70.
5. Garcia DM, Sheehan MC. Extreme Weather-driven Disasters and Children's Health. *Int J Health Serv*. 2016 Jan;46(1):79–105.
6. Usami M, Lomboy MFT, Satake N,

- Estrada CAM, Kodama M, Gregorio Jr ER, et al. Addressing challenges in children's mental health in disaster-affected areas in Japan and the Philippines – highlights of the training program by the National Center for Global Health and Medicine. *BMC Proc.* 2018 Dec;12(S14):65.
7. Seneviratne SI, Nicholls N, Easterling D, Goodess CM, Kanae S, Kossin J, et al. Changes in Climate Extremes and their Impacts on the Natural Physical Environment. In: Field CB, Barros V, Stocker TF, Dahe Q, editors. *Managing the Risks of Extreme Events and Disasters to Advance Climate Change Adaptation* [Internet]. 1st ed. Cambridge University Press; 2012 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. p. 109–230. Available from: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/CBO9781139177245A030/type/book_part
 8. Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (Ippc). *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Internet]. 1st ed. Cambridge University Press; 2023 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. Available from: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/97811009325844/type/book>
 9. Duan Y, Xiong J, Cheng W, Li Y, Wang N, Shen G, et al. Increasing Global Flood Risk in 2005–2020 from a Multi-Scale Perspective. *Remote Sens.* 2022 Nov 3;14(21):5551.
 10. Karim M, Mimura N. Impacts of climate change and sea-level rise on cyclonic storm surge floods in Bangladesh. *Glob Environ Change.* 2008 Aug;18(3):490–500.
 11. Ahmed HU, Alam MT, Hossain T, Rabbani MG, Alam MWA. Mental Health Service After Disaster: Bangladesh Perspective. *Eur Psychiatry.* 2015 Mar;30:1881.
 12. Morshed S, Rahman MdT, Rokonuzzaman S, Hossain A. The Economic Impact of Monsoon Flood and Its Spillover on the Households of Bangladesh. *J Sustain Dev.* 2022 Mar 9;15(3):23.
 13. Matsuyama A, Khan FA, Khalequzzaman Md. Bangladesh Public Health Issues and Implications to Flood Risk Reduction. In: Chan EYY, Shaw R, editors. *Public Health and Disasters* [Internet]. Singapore: Springer Singapore; 2020 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. p. 115–28. (Disaster Risk Reduction). Available from: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-15-0924-7_8
 14. Cianconi P, Betrò S, Janiri L. The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health: A Systematic Descriptive Review. *Front Psychiatry.* 2020 Mar 6;11:74.
 15. Dean JG, Stain HJ. Mental health impact for adolescents living with prolonged drought. *Aust J Rural Health.* 2010 Feb;18(1):32–7.
 16. Mambrey V, Wermuth I, Böse-O'Reilly S. Auswirkungen von Extremwetterereignissen auf die psychische Gesundheit von Kindern und Jugendlichen. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz.* 2019 May;62(5):599–604.
 17. Bennett C, Friel S. Impacts of Climate Change on Inequities in Child Health. *Children.* 2014 Dec 3;1(3):461–73.
 18. Schürr A, Elbel J, Hieronimi A, Auer I, Coenen M, Böse-O'Reilly S. Mental health in adolescents after experiencing a flood event in Bavaria, Germany—A qualitative interview study. *Front Public Health.* 2023 Sep 6;11:1210072.
 19. Hieronimi A, Elbel J, Schneider M, Wermuth I, Schulte-Körne G, Nowak D, et al. A Qualitative Study to Explain the Factors Influencing Mental Health after a Flooding. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022 Dec 22;20(1):134.
 20. Nahar N, Blomstedt Y, Wu B, Kandarina I, Trisnantoro L, Kinsman J. Increasing the provision of mental health care for vulnerable, disaster-affected people in Bangladesh. *BMC Public Health.* 2014 Dec;14(1):708.
 21. Nieswiadomy RMB. *Foundations of nursing research* [Internet]. Pearson;

- 2018 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. Available from:
[//library.prasonmtc.org%2Findex.php%3Fp%3Dshow_detail%26id%3D585](http://library.prasonmtc.org%2Findex.php%3Fp%3Dshow_detail%26id%3D585)
22. Gough B, Lyons A. The Future of Qualitative Research in Psychology: Accentuating the Positive. *Integr Psychol Behav Sci.* 2016 Jun;50(2):234–43.
 23. Callary B, Rathwell S, Young B. Insights on the Process of Using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis in a Sport Coaching Research Project. *Qual Rep [Internet].* 2015 Feb 10 [cited 2024 Sep 29]; Available from: <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol20/iss2/6/>
 24. Smith JA, Osborn M. Interpretative phenomenological analysis as a useful methodology for research on the lived experience of pain. *Br J Pain.* 2015 Feb;9(1):41–2.
 25. NASA Applied Sciences. Bangladesh Flooding August 2024. 2024 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. Bangladesh Flooding August 2024 | NASA Applied Sciences. Available from: <http://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/what-we-do/disasters/disasters-activations/bangladesh-flooding-august-2024>
 26. Sandelowski M. Qualitative analysis: What it is and how to begin. *Res Nurs Health.* 1995 Aug;18(4):371–5.
 27. Crouch M, McKenzie H. The logic of small samples in interview-based qualitative research. *Soc Sci Inf.* 2006 Dec;45(4):483–99.
 28. Charmaz K. Premises, Principles, and Practices in Qualitative Research: Revisiting the Foundations. *Qual Health Res.* 2004 Sep;14(7):976–93.
 29. Green J, Thorogood N. Qualitative methods for health research. London: SAGE Publications; 2004. 262 p. (Introducing qualitative methods).
 30. Modell J. *Biography and Society: The Life History Approach in the Social Sciences.*: Edited by Daniel Bertaux. HillsBeverly, Calif.: Sage Publications, 1981. 314 pp. Hardbound, \$22.50. *Oral Hist Rev.* 1982 Jan 1;10(1):154–6.
 31. Guest G, MacQueen K, Namey E. *Applied Thematic Analysis [Internet].* 2455 Teller Road, Thousand Oaks California 91320 United States: SAGE Publications, Inc.; 2012 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. Available from: <https://methods.sagepub.com/book/applied-thematic-analysis>
 32. Hieronimi A, Elbel J, Schneider M, Wermuth I, Schulte-Körne G, Nowak D, et al. A Qualitative Study to Explain the Factors Influencing Mental Health after a Flooding. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022 Dec 22;20(1):134.
 33. Rädiker S, Kuckartz U. *Analyse qualitativer Daten mit MAXQDA: Text, Audio und Video [Internet].* Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden; 2019 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-658-22095-2>
 34. Stamann C, Janssen M, Schreier M. Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse – Versuch einer Begriffsbestimmung und Systematisierung. *Forum Qual Sozialforschung Forum Qual Soc Res.* 2016 Sep 9;Vol 17:No 3 (2016).
 35. CDC. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2023 [cited 2024 Sep 29]. Helping Your Child Cope with a Disaster | CDC. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/childrenindisasters/children-disaster-help.html>
 36. Mambrey V, Wermuth I, Böse-O'Reilly S. Auswirkungen von Extremwetterereignissen auf die psychische Gesundheit von Kindern und Jugendlichen. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz.* 2019 May;62(5):599–604.
 37. Kar N. Psychological impact of disasters on children: review of assessment and interventions. *World J Pediatr.* 2009 Feb;5(1):5–11.
 38. Hieronimi A, Elbel J, Schneider M, Wermuth I, Schulte-Körne G, Nowak D, et al. A Qualitative Study to Explain the Factors Influencing Mental Health after a Flooding. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022 Dec 22;20(1):134.
 39. Hieronimi A, Elbel J, Schneider M, Wermuth I, Schulte-Körne G, Nowak D, et al. A Qualitative Study to Explain the Factors Influencing Mental Health

- after a Flooding. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 Dec 22;20(1):134.
40. Schürr A, Elbel J, Hieronimi A, Auer I, Coenen M, Böse-O'Reilly S. Mental health in adolescents after experiencing a flood event in Bavaria, Germany—A qualitative interview study. *Front Public Health*. 2023 Sep 6;11:1210072.
 41. Blank-Gorki V, Breuer F, Fegert AK, Neumann T, Niedermeier M, Rielage T, et al. Komplexe Gefahren- und Schadenslagen mit Kindern und Jugendlichen: Häufigkeit in Deutschland und Analyse psychosozialer Versorgungsstrukturen. *Notf Rettungsmedizin*. 2020 Aug;23(5):364–9.
 42. Daniel A, Michaela C. Mental health and health-related quality of life in victims of the 2013 flood disaster in Germany – A longitudinal study of health-related flood consequences and evaluation of institutionalized low-threshold psycho-social support. *Int J Disaster Risk Reduct*. 2021 May;58:102179.
 43. Tong A, Sainsbury P, Craig J. Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): a 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *Int J Qual Health Care*. 2007 Sep 16;19(6):349–57.